

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-51-IG-10% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221029
Vial:	16	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 51
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 13:33:55 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:50:21 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.873	5407959	49.57	306144
2	11.628	5502806	50.43	284757

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-57-IG-10% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221029
Vial:	17	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 57
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 13:54:33 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:50:04 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.848	19386099	97.47	1098845
2	11.640	504110	2.53	25933